

Henk Alkemade, Gustavo Candela, Steven Claeysens, Giovanni Colavizza, Selda Eren, Nuno Freire, Alba Irollo, Antoine Isaac, Jörg Lehmann, Clemens Neudecker, Giulia Osti, Daniel van Strien, Melvin Wevers

Template: Datasheet for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets

Version 2 – March 2025

This template is the second version of the template to describe Cultural Heritage datasets that was introduced in Alkemade et al. 2023 (<https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>). The main structure of the first version followed Gebru's (2021) and Pushkarna's templates (2022); the second version introduces some more differences, especially as an attempt to align better with the DCAT Application Profile for data portals which is getting traction in Europe (DCAT-AP).¹ The superscripts added to section headings refer to items in the bibliography at the very end, which have inspired the section by providing explanations and/or discussions about its topic.

Notes on filling the template. This template is structured in three levels, the top-level providing fields for a high-level description of a dataset along a specific dimension, and the lower levels allowing a datasheet creator to indicate more specific details, possibly using more controlled expressions. Cultural heritage datasets are heterogeneous, therefore not every item of the template fits; users of the template should decide on what is helpful and what can be discarded. Not all parts of the template will be uniformly relevant to all datasets or equally applicable to features within a single dataset. However, to achieve compatibility with DCAT-AP, it is recommended to fill the fields which are marked as DCAT-AP-mandatory^{DCAT-AP:M}. For the sake of completeness, if you are certain that a field does not apply to the dataset at hand (as opposed to a situation where you simply do not have the information) please fill this field with "Not applicable".

Title^{DCAT-AP:M}

[Documentation of "Förderprogramm Filmerbe", the national funding programme for film heritage digitisation in Germany](#)

Description^c and Motivation^{b,f}

[Provide a brief descriptive overview of the dataset ('at a glance').^{DCAT-AP:M} Briefly summarise the dataset, its intended use and the supported tasks. Give an overview of how and why the dataset was created. The summary should describe the domain, topic,

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/dcat-ap>

genre covered, keywords, and other relevant metadata. Clearly articulate the reasons for creating the dataset and promote transparency about funding interests. For what purpose was the dataset created? Was there a specific task in mind? Was there a specific gap that needed to be filled? Who created the dataset (e.g., which team, research group) and on behalf of which entity (e.g., company, institution, organisation)? Who funded the creation of the dataset?]

DFF - Deutsches Filminstitut & Filmmuseum documents the ongoing digitisation efforts and outcomes of the German [Förderprogramm Filmerbe](#) (running from 2019 to 2029) where currently 1,500 films have been digitised or are in the progress of digitisation. While this information is publicly available in the form of press releases and info "flags" on [filmportal.de](#), a complete structured overview of all film digitisation projects is available in this dataset. It contains amongst other data the title, other identifying filmographic information, the [filmportal.de](#) link to the film, the year in which the digitisation funding was granted, the name of the institution responsible for the digitisation and the information whether the project is completed. For feature films longer than 60 minutes, the first five minutes are publicly available on [filmportal.de](#) and the respective link is included in the data.

Homepage

https://www.filmportal.de/movies?f%5B0%5D=movie_digitization_supporter%3A1016

<https://www.ffa.de/foerderprogramm-filmerbe.html>

Repository^{DCAT-AP:M}

[E.g., if the dataset is hosted on GitHub or has a GitHub homepage, add URL here.]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690750>

Papers and/or Other References

[If the dataset was introduced by a paper or there was a paper written describing the dataset, add URL here.]

Publisher

[Either the individual publisher or the responsible organisation should be provided - preferably the latter.]

[DFF - Deutsches Filminstitut & Filmmuseum](#)

Point of Contact

[If known, name, email and/or ORCID of at least one person or organisational contact the reader can reach for questions and comments about the dataset and/or the datasheet. This is especially relevant as datasets can change, and datasheets should be conceived of as flexible and dynamic objects which change according to the version of a dataset documented by them. Therefore, please indicate a reliable contact in order to enable the incorporation of responses and comments into a new version.]

dokumentation-filmerbe@dff.film

Supported Tasks and Shared Tasks^c

[For each of the tasks identified for this dataset, give a brief description of the task, metrics, and suggested models. Also provide reference to any shared task the dataset is part of.]

AI Category

[The category of the AI application that the dataset is suitable for. This field is free text but it is advised to refer to shared vocabularies like the AI4Culture² one (“Automation”, “Copywriting”, “Generative Art”, “Image editing”...) or the HuggingFace taxonomy of tasks.³]

[Question answering](#)
[Summarization](#)

Type of Cultural Heritage Application

[The type of cultural heritage application that the resource is applied in or could be relevant for. This field is free text, but it is advised to refer to shared vocabularies like TADIRAH⁴ or the AI4Culture categories (Collection management, Collection search, Metadata enrichment).]

[Statistical data on cultural heritage digitisation efforts and outcomes is rare. While the outcomes, i.e. digital items, are likely to be publicly available via Europeana or national/regional online platforms, information on the scope and progress of a programme are usually either not tracked or only available internally to the funding body. With the documentation of the Förderprogramm Filmerbe the respective dataset offers insights](#)

² <https://ai4culture.eu/>

³ <https://huggingface.co/tasks>

⁴ <https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/>

into the impact of the funding in terms of films as a cultural heritage asset available in digital format. The fact that the documentation is ongoing until 2029 makes this dataset especially interesting with regard to releasing updates and tracking progress. Linking the filmographic information of the film work on filmportal.de with the administrative information on which institution received funding, and ultimately documenting the information on the digital manifestation offers opportunities for further analysis like:

- Which “parts” of the German film heritage are chosen for digitisation? (e.g. by topic, decade, cast/crew ...)
- Combining the data on completed digitisation with other sources like public screening or television broadcast information to examine the impact on public accessibility of the films after digitisation
- Development of the number of digitisations over the course of the programme (e.g. did the number of funded projects increase or decrease?)

(Cultural Heritage) Application Example

[Specific instance of application (link to a project page, paper or other).]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15788945>

Distribution^b

[Dataset creators should provide answers to the following points: distribution information, dissemination strategy, licences, DOIs, third party involvement and restrictions.]

Dataset Curators^c

[List the people involved in collecting the dataset and their affiliation(s). Dataset curators are encouraged to insert some information about their positionality here, e.g. in the form of a short bio containing information on their formation, role and function within the CHI or project and the task(s) with which they were entrusted during the creation of the dataset.]

The staff working on the documentation of FFE digitisation have collected the contents of this dataset, namely:

Kathleen Benecke, DFF

Natalie Filipiak, DFF

Jaana Hufnagel, DFF
Kristina Rose, DFF

Licensing Information^c

[Provide the licence for the current data distribution and link to the licence(s) webpage(s) if available.]

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Citation Information^c

[Provide the BibTeX-formatted reference for the dataset. If the dataset has a DOI or other kind of persistent identifier, please provide it here.]

DFF - Deutsches Filminstitut & Filmmuseum. (2025). Dokumentation des "Förderprogramm Filmerbe", das nationale Digitalisierungsprogramm für Filmerbe in Deutschland (1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15690751>

Contributions^c

[List the people who have contributed to this dataset as well as those who have curated and published it.]

Composition^{b,e}

[Provide dataset consumers with the information they need to make informed decisions about using the dataset for their chosen tasks. What medium is the dataset (image, video, text, web archive, etc.)?^e What do the instances that comprise the dataset represent (e.g., documents, photos, people, countries)? Are there multiple types of instances (e.g., movies, users, and ratings; people and interactions between them; nodes and edges)? Provide information on the languages represented in the dataset. What formats are used in the dataset (.xml, .json, etc.)?]

Data Category

[Describe the media associated with the dataset, e.g. an OCR dataset is associated with image and text.]

[text, video](#)

Object Type

[Indicate a more specialised type of CH objects than the category above, like 'newspaper', 'painting', 'metadata'. NB: using keywords or concepts from a relevant standard vocabulary like AAT here will help make the dataset better findable.]

[metadata](#)

Dataset Structure^c

[Provide one or more typical examples of data instances, a systematic description of the dataset structure or schema, and the data splits which can be used for machine learning tasks.]

Data Instances^c

[Provide an example (possibly a data snippet) and brief description of a typical instance in the dataset. What metadata are available for the dataset items?]

[see "Data Fields" section](#)

Data Fields^{c,f}

[List and describe the fields present in the dataset. Mention their data type, and whether they are used as input or output in any of the tasks the dataset currently supports. If the data has e.g. span indices, describe their attributes, such as whether they are at the character or word level, whether they are contiguous or not, etc. Similarly, if the dataset contains IDs, state whether their structure has an inherent meaning, and whether they should be interpreted as a mapping to other datasets or pointing to relationships between data points.

NB: if the list conforms to an existing standard or best practice, it is recommended to use the "compliance with standard" field below.]

Compliance with Standard(s)

[A standard data model or schema and/or established data practice, for example W3C Web Annotation, that the dataset conforms to.]

[n/a](#)

Data Splits^c

[Describe and name machine learning splits in the dataset if there are any. Describe any criteria for splitting the data, if used. If there are differences between the splits (e.g. if the training annotations are machine-generated and the development and test ones are created by humans, or if different numbers of annotators contributed to each example), describe them here. Provide the sizes of each split. If appropriate, provide any descriptive statistics for the features, such as average length. Are there recommended data splits (e.g., training, development/validation, testing)? If so, please provide a description of these splits, explaining the rationale behind them.]

n/a

Languages^c

[Explicitly mention the languages present in the dataset (possibly in broad terms, e.g. translations between several pairs of European languages). Describe relevant details about specifics of the language using e.g. BCP-47 codes.⁵]

Column headers: de, en

Cells "Titel / Title": mul

Cells "Gattung / Category of film": de

Cells "Förderung / Funding": de

Cells "Quelle / Source": de, en

Cells: "Fördersparte / Funding category": de

Descriptive Statistics

[The information presented in this section should be chosen on the basis of whether it tells something valuable. Be reminded that it depends on the intended purpose of a dataset whether the numbers and metrics provided can be of use. How large is the dataset, both in cardinality and in disk storage?^e What are its key descriptive statistics per field? Consider which statistics should be put into the bias section below to avoid overlap. For example, if some objects in a dataset don't have metadata about their creators, this can be flagged in the general statistics as a quality issue that possibly hinders application development. If there is a gender imbalance in the available creators this could be indicated in the section about biases.]

[See description on Zenodo](#)

⁵ <https://tools.ietf.org/html/bcp47>

Data Collection Process^{b,e,f}

[Elicit information that may help researchers and practitioners to re-use this dataset or create alternative datasets with similar characteristics.]

Curation Rationale^{c,e,f}

[What need motivated the creation of this dataset? What were some of the reasons underlying the major choices involved in putting it together?]

DFF has the official mandate to document the outcomes of the funding programme Förderprogramm Filmerbe which is financed by the Federal Government Commissioner for Culture and the Media (BKM), the FFA and the federal states. The documentation dataset serves the unambiguous identification of films as well as tracking the progress and the outcomes of the digitisation projects.

Source Data^{c,f}

[This section describes the source data (e.g. news text and headlines, translated sentences,...).]

Initial Data Collection and Normalisation^c

[Describe the data collection process. Describe any criteria for data selection, filtering or harvesting (in particular, list any keywords or search terms used). If possible and relevant, include runtime information for the collection process. If data was collected from other pre-existing datasets, link to the source here. If the data was modified or normalised after being collected (e.g. if the data is word-tokenized), describe the process and the tools used.]

The data is collected from four three different data sources: Identifying information about the film works, so called filmographical data, comes from DFF's central filmographic database. The data on the specific digitisation project comes from press releases by the FFA. Digitization progress and outcome information (the manifestation information) stems from forms filled out by the applicants and provided to DFF. Lastly, the duration information of the resulting opening sequences provided to DFF are extracted from the video files.

Source Data Producers^c

[State whether the source data were produced by humans or machine generated and provide a description for them. If available, include self-reported demographic or identity information for the source data creators, but avoid inferring this information. Instead, state that this information is unknown. See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender.]

[humans](#)

Digitisation Pipeline^e

[Indicate information (paradata) on the digitization process, which can be relevant for reuse; for example the motivation for digitisation (e.g. conservation, research project, or else) and/or technical metadata such as the image capture equipment and software/parameters used for any OCR/HTR processing and/or the level of quality of the results. If applicable, describe in what way digitisation presents another layer of selection of the whole of a collection available in a cultural heritage institution; provide selection criteria and metrics that show how it has influenced the transformation of this collection into the current dataset (e.g. what part has been digitised and what not).^e State if there was no such selection.]

[n/a](#)

Preprocessing and Cleaning^{b,f}

[Provide dataset consumers with the information they need to determine whether the “raw” data has been processed in ways that are compatible with their chosen tasks.]

[Raw data was cleaned with OpenRefine for the publication process. Transformation history is available in .json format. Only a subset of the columns from the FFE documentation process is available in the public dataset.](#)

Annotations^{c,f}

[If the dataset contains annotations which are not part of the initial data collection, describe them in the following paragraphs. If annotations are published as a separate dataset (with its own datasheet being the one filled here) then please reflect the information below in the fields above, especially “Initial Data Collection and Normalisation” and “Source Data Producers?”.]

n/a

Annotation Process^c

[If applicable, describe the annotation process and any tools used, or state otherwise. Describe the amount of data annotated, if not all. Have the annotations been aggregated? What are the limitations of the annotation method? Describe or reference annotation guidelines provided to the annotators. If available, provide inter-annotator statistics. Describe any annotation validation processes.]

Annotators^{c,f}

[If annotations were collected for the source data (such as class labels or syntactic parsers), state whether the annotations were produced by humans or machine generated. Describe the people or systems who originally created the annotations and their selection criteria, if applicable. Is socio-demographic information on the annotators available? Can the annotators be assigned to a specific population group? Is the socio-demographic data on the annotators available to the users of the dataset? If available, include self-reported demographic or identity information for the annotators, but avoid inferring this information. Instead, state that this information is unknown. See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender.]

Crowd Labour^{e,f}

[Describe the conditions under which the data was annotated (for example, if the annotators were crowdworkers, state what platform was used, or if the data was found, what website the data was found on). If compensation was provided, include that information here.]

Data Provenance^{e,f}

[If applicable, provide additional information on the aspects of provenance that have impacted the data collection, for example ownership, rights, licences and other obligations associated with sources of data.]

n/a

Use of Linked Open Data, Controlled Vocabularies, Multilingual Ontologies/Taxonomies

[Describe linked open data schemes, controlled vocabularies, ontologies and taxonomies if used during the establishment of the dataset.]

Vocabulary used for indicating the category of film:

<https://xtree-public.digicult-verbund.de/vocnet/?uriVocItem=http://filmportal.vocnet.org/category/&startNode=c00061&lang=de&d=n>

Version Information^f

[Provide information on the dataset version being the subject of this datasheet. Alternatively, provide a release date and a date when the dataset was last updated as well as information on whether there was a previous version of the dataset published before. If relevant, describe which versioning policy drives growing or changing datasets (e.g. systematisation, subsetting for specific purposes). Indicate if the status of previous versions has become deprecated. If the new version differs substantially from the previous one, especially if a dataset grows over time, it is recommended to provide an adapted datasheet.]

Release Date

[If applicable, fill the time stamp of the date of release of this version.]

2025-08-07

Date of Modification

[If applicable, fill the time stamp of the date of (minor) modification of this version.]

n/a

Checksums

[Provide checksums over here (with a clear mention of the algorithm, e.g. MD5 and SHA256).]

n/a

Update Periodicity

[Is the dataset foreseen to be updated? If so, how frequently?]

Updated annually

Maintenance^{b,f}

[Dataset creators are encouraged to plan for dataset maintenance and communicate this plan to dataset consumers. Three suggestions to communicate this: a) *Actively Maintained* – This dataset will be actively maintained, including but not limited to updates to the data. b) *Limited Maintenance* – The data will not be updated, but any technical issues will be addressed c) *No maintenance*.]

Actively Maintained

Examples and Considerations for Using the Data^{b,f}

[Dataset creators are encouraged to reflect on the tasks for which the dataset should and should not be used. This section can also provide guidelines on usage.]

Ethical Considerations

Personal and Other Sensitive Information^{c,e,f}

[Sensitive data are better not expressed through quantitative information, but are recommended to be explained narratively. Descriptions might answer the following questions: Who or what are depicted in the dataset? If the dataset depicts people, are any specific subgroups of people represented? Are any specific individuals personally identifiable? If the dataset depicts people, are any individuals still living? Does this project comply with GDPR and privacy laws in the countries where it will be shared? Does this dataset pertain to a difficult history? If so, what extra precautions are being taken? Describe other people represented or mentioned in the data. Where possible, link to references for the information given.

State whether the dataset uses identity categories and, if so, how the information is used. Describe where this information comes from (i.e. self-reporting, collecting from profiles, inferring, etc.). See Larson, 2017^d for using identity categories as variables, particularly gender. State whether the data is linked to individuals and whether those individuals can likely be identified in the dataset, either directly or indirectly (i.e., in combination with other data). State whether the dataset contains other data that might be considered sensitive (e.g., data that reveals racial or ethnic origins, sexual orientations, religious beliefs, political opinions or union memberships, or locations; financial or health data; biometric or genetic data; forms of government identification, such as social security

numbers; criminal history). If efforts were made to anonymise the data, describe the anonymisation process. Parts of this information provided here might be placed instead in the section about biases below.]

n/a

Discussion of Biases^c

[Provide descriptions of specific biases that are likely to be reflected in the data, and state whether any steps were taken to reduce their impact. See Blodgett et al., 2020^a for a general discussion of the topic in NLP. If analyses have been run quantifying these biases, please add brief summaries and links to the studies here.]

Biased or harmful language can appear as part of the film title information. Since these are the original titles used for publication, no changes to the titles were made in the data to allow for clear identification and findability.

Potential Societal Impact of Using the Dataset^c

[Discuss some of the ways you believe the use of this dataset could impact society. The statement should include positive outlooks, such as outlining how technologies developed through its use may facilitate new knowledge creation (e.g., if it contains useful data for a low-resource or under-represented language). It should also discuss risks. These risks may range from making important decisions more opaque to people who are affected by the technology, to reinforcing existing harmful biases (whose specifics should be discussed in the previous section), among other considerations. Indicate whether impacted communities have been consulted in the process of curating and publishing the dataset and/or should be involved at reuse stage.]

The dataset allows for public insights into the outcomes of a publicly funded cultural heritage digitisation programme and is thus impacting reporting and critical review of such programmes. Furthermore, it could serve as a benchmark for future digitisation progress tracking and ultimately makes the necessity of public funding for the availability and accessibility of film heritage much more tangible.

Examples of Datasets, Publications and Models that (re-)use the Dataset

[Reuse is defined as use of the data regardless of when it is used, the purpose, the characteristics of the data and its user (van de Sandt et al., 2019^g). If you know that the dataset has been used to create and publish other datasets, if a researcher uses this data for a particular purpose (e.g., assessing its quality) or if there is a model which has been trained on this dataset, add URL here.

“Publications” includes, for instance, other datasheets and (Jupyter) notebooks.]

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15788945>

Known Non-Ethical Limitations^c

[If studies of the datasets have outlined other limitations of the dataset, such as annotation artefacts, please outline and cite them here.]

n/a

Unanticipated Uses made of this Dataset^f

[Datasets may be used in contexts that they were not conceived for. As this can open positive opportunities that were not thought of, or cause issues which are specific to a dataset, it is recommended to indicate here the unintended uses that one wants to inform re-users about.]

n/a

Bibliography Used for Establishing this Template

^aBlodgett, S. L., Barocas, S., Daumé III, H., & Wallach, H. (2020). Language (Technology) is Power: A Critical Survey of “Bias” in NLP. *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 5454–5476.

<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.485>

^bGebru, T., Morgenstern, J., Vecchione, B., Vaughan, J. W., Wallach, H., Daumé III, H., & Crawford, K. (2021). Datasheets for Datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(12), 86–92.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3458723>

^cHugging Face Dataset Card Creation Guide,

https://github.com/huggingface/datasets/blob/main/templates/README_guide.md

^dLarson, B. N. (2017). Gender as a Variable in Natural-Language Processing: Ethical Considerations. *EthNLP@EACL*. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1%2FW17-1601>

^eLee, B. C. G. (2023). The 'Collections as ML Data' Checklist for Machine Learning & Cultural Heritage. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24765>

^fPushkarna, M., Zaldivar, A., & Kjartansson, O. (2022). Data Cards: Purposeful and Transparent Dataset Documentation for Responsible AI. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 1776–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533231>

^gvan de Sandt, S., Dallmeier-Tiessen, S., Lavasa, A. & Petras, V. (2019). The Definition of Reuse. *Data Science Journal*, 18(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2019-022>